

Interactions in Quantum Mechanics

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In classical mechanics, interactions follow Newton's second law which is equivalent to a conservation of energy equation with a potential $V(x)$ for conservative forces. The Schrodinger equation, we argue, allows for two kinds of interactions. The first is like the classical situation and involves average kinetic energy as part of a classical conservation equation with $V(x)$. This is also associated with a $\langle p \text{ rms} \rangle$ i.e. root mean square momentum, which is identical to classical momentum. There exists, however, also $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = \sum_p p P(p/x)$ with $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ ($W(x)$ is the wavefunction). This momentum is responsible for dW/dx and in turn the change in spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ i.e. quantum humps. $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$, like p_{rms} follows from interactions of the particle with $V(x)$ in a bound system and possibly other reasons, but does not follow Newton's law.

In this note, we consider the more general case of $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ which appears in the Aharonov-Bohm problem. It seems one may form a generalized $\langle p \text{ general at } x \rangle = A(x) + \langle p \text{ usual at } x \rangle$ i.e. calculate various pieces of $\langle p \text{ general at } x \rangle$ which govern the spatial density, i.e. interference, without necessarily contributing to $KE_{ave}(x)$ in $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ ((1)). In particular, $A(x)$, the magnetic vector potential behaves like a portion of $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and is involved in interference, but plays no role in ((1)). We suggest two different kinds of interactions may occur in a quantum system. The first is the usual Newton type interaction applied to averages, but a second involves interactions that create $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ which does not behave according to Newtonian mechanics. For a bound state problem with $V(x)$, both types of interactions exist, thus one has two "momenta", p_{rms} and $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$, with only the latter obeying Newtonian mechanics. For the time-independent Schrodinger equation, Newtonian conservation of energy applies only to average values such as $KE_{ave}(x)$ and $V(x)$ which is itself an average, we argue. Given that there exists microscopic motion and a distribution $a(p) \exp(ipx)$, these may give rise to non-Newtonian behaviour and interactions other than the usual $-dV/dx$ in ((1)).

Phase in Quantum Mechanics

It seems a free quantum particle wavefunction (relative conditional probability) $\exp(ipx)$ already suggests the idea of an "interaction" beyond Newtonian mechanics. $\exp(ipx)$ represents a constant momentum p and hence constant kinetic energy $pp/2m$. There is no "force" accelerating p , yet physical results consistent with an interaction occur because $\exp(ipx)$ may obtain a relative phase if the particle traverses one path versus another. These effects may be observed in a two particle interference pattern. In previous notes, we argued that a classical particle has an equal probability to occur at any position x if there is no potential. A free quantum particle is somewhat different. The modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ is 1, meaning there is equal density for the particle to be at any x , but $\exp(ipx)$ is not equivalent to a real, positive constant - it includes cycling (a wavelength). It is as if a free quantum particle somehow "interacts" as it moves through space tracking this as a phase.

For a bound quantum system, the time-independent Schrodinger equation applies. In terms of averages, this is the classical conservation equation:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

Where $KE_{ave}(x) = \sum \over p \quad p^2/2m P(p/x)$ with $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ and $W(x)=\sum \over p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

The time-dependent Schrodinger equation differs from classical physics due to a momentum distribution established at each x based on $\exp(ipx)$ (free particle conditional probability) which represents physics beyond classical mechanics (with no internal motion etc). ((1)) implies Newtonian mechanics need only apply to average quantities such as $KE_{ave}(x)$ and p rms. For example, one may calculate $\langle p^2 \text{ at } x \rangle = \sum \over p p^2 P(p/x)$ and $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = \sum \over p p P(p/x)$. The latter does not obey Newtonian mechanics and involves backwards and forwards motion within each wavelength. There seems to be two distinct interaction behaviours occurring. The first is the Newtonian situation which leads to ((1)), and the second an interaction producing $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$. In a previous note, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$, which is like a two vector, accounts for these two interaction modes. The first term $\cos(px)$ applies to p^2 or even powers of p , and the second $i \sin(px)$ to odd. So we argue, using $\exp(ipx)$ already incorporates the idea of a two interaction schemes, even for a problem with only $V(x)$.

In a previous note (1), we argued that

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i dx (-id \ln W/dx)) \text{ where } -id \ln W/dx = \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle. \quad ((2))$$

We suggested this may be a general quantum principle. In other words, the second type of interaction leading to $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ is responsible for the creation of spatial density humps because $\text{spatial density} = W^*(x)W(x)$. Humps in quantum mechanical density are due to a second interaction, unlike the usual Newtonian conservation of energy process. To see specifically why this may be the case, consider $(p) \exp(ipx) + (-p) \exp(-ipx) = 2i \sin(px)$. In classical mechanics or classical statistical mechanics, the average of a particle moving forward and backward with p is 0, but is $\sin(px)$ in quantum bound states. It is only the average over a wavelength that is zero. It is exactly this behaviour which gives rise to $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ which in turn creates quantum humps, we argue.

Beyond V(x)

In the previous section, we argued that there exist two momenta in quantum mechanics, p rms and $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$, both linked to $V(x)$, yet both related to different physical manifestations. p rms exhibits acceleration while $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ creates density humps. In the Bohm Aharonov scenario, it seems one may generalize $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ if a magnetic potential $A(x)$ is present, but one still has the two interaction components. The generalized $\langle p \text{ at } x \text{ gen} \rangle$ continues to control humps through ((2)) and there still exists a conservation of energy equation ((1)). The difference is that $A(x)$

contributes to $\langle p \text{ at } x \text{ gen} \rangle$, but not to the conservation equation if gradient curl A is 0 i.e. if there is no B magnetic field and thus no work done by this field.

As a first step, consider the Bohm Aharonov scenario as presented in (2):

$(p-eA)(p-eA) W + V(r) W = E W$ ((3)) where $V(r)$ = Coulomb potential + other scalar potential, A is a vector potential and p is -i gradient. It is shown in (2) (and may be verified in a straightforward manner) that:

$W=W_0(r) \exp(i g(r))$ where $g(r)= \int_{r_0}^r A(r) dr$ solves ((3)).

Thus, the magnetic potential adds a phase to the wavefunction. For gradient curl A = 0, there is no B and no magnetic Lorentz force or work. ((3)) collapses to:

$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W + VW = EW$ ((4)) i.e. the usual Schrodinger equation without A.

Here, it seems that the two interactions are displayed. First, the quantum particle “interacts” with A because a phase is added. If there were no interaction, it would seem there should be no presence of A in the solution. Secondly, the usual average Newtonian conservation equation ((4)) applies, but only to the part of the wavefunction not related to A. Thus:

$\langle p \text{ at } x \text{ gen} \rangle = \langle p \text{ from } V \text{ at } x \rangle + A$ ((5))

The average momentum is now more complicated and describes interactions with both A and $V(x)$. In (3), it is specifically argued that virtual photons from A interact with virtual photons from the quantum particle, without any work being done to the particle.

From ((5)), one may see that the generalized $\langle p \text{ at } x \text{ gen} \rangle$ again controls quantum humps:

$W(x+dx)= W(x) \exp[i dx (A -id/dx \ln W)]$ ((6))

Thus, the Bohm Aharonov scenario seems to be a generalized case demonstrating that interactions with a potential may be of two kinds. For the usual $V(x)$, one has both Newtonian interactions and $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$, while A a magnetic vector potential which creates no force, contributes only to $\langle p \text{ at } x \text{ gen} \rangle$ which affects the quantum hump pattern.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in quantum mechanics, two interaction schemes occur related to the two components of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $i \sin(px)$. The first is related to the Newtonian conservation of energy and the second to $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ which is part of $W(x+dx)=W(x)\exp(i dx \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle dx)$ and controls quantum humps because spatial density= $W^*(x)W(x)$. A usual potential $V(x)$ involves both. In the Bohm-Aharonov scenario, the magnetic potential A is such that there is no magnetic field and so no B field work. Thus, A should not contribute to the Newtonian type

interaction, but it still contributes to $\langle p \text{ at } x \text{ general} \rangle$ i.e. a phase and one has the generalized equation: $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(ix \langle p \text{ at } x \text{ general} \rangle) = W(x) \exp(ix A) \exp(i (-id \ln W/dx))$. It seems that the particle should be interacting with A, otherwise A should not appear in the solution, but it only interacts in the $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ hump controlling manner.

References

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